

The Illusion of Affordability: Teen Perceptions of Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) Payment

Options

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Abstract

As Buy Now, Pay Later (BNPL) services grow in volume in digital and physical commerce, widespread concerns have developed regarding the direct influence on consumer perceptions – notable affordability and financial risk – especially among young individuals. This study aims to investigate how high school students, who are exposed to the payment method but lack eligibility to utilize it, perceive BNPL compared to traditional, upfront payments. Using a mixed-methods design, 72 high school students participated in two simulated purchasing scenarios in which similar products were offered at the same total price: one scenario represented BNPL installments while the other represented a full, upfront payment. Participants responded to Likert-scale questions to measure variables, including affordability, emotional burden, and financial risk, while supporting choices with qualitative discussion. Results highlighted that students perceived BNPL installments as more affordable with minimal emotional burden compared to upfront payments at the same total price point. In addition, 76% of participants reported BNPL made products appear more affordable, noting the smaller installments and flexible payment period options. Students who identified in higher household income ranges demonstrated a reduced preference towards BNPL adoption. Hence, the findings reveal how installment payments may influence high school students' perceptions even before BNPL eligibility, impacting future usage. Consequently, the importance of financial literacy education for students is vital to create more informed decision making as students become independent.

Introduction

Across the nation, American consumers have flocked to short-term, unsecured credit – rising the total debt held to nearly \$1 trillion – in order to fund a diverse range of purchases (Maggio et

al., 2022). Over the years, various payment methods involving debt financing, like credit cards, supported the immense volume of purchases made by consumers who may not have full access to the funds required for desired goods or services (Saiag, 2020). More recently, an innovative, digital method of payment has emerged, permitting consumers to finance their purchases with little to no interest and low credit risk: buy now, pay later (BNPL) offers appealing terms without sacrificing flexibility and convenience, particularly to young individuals (Mat & Munir, 2025).

In essence, BNPL – primarily offered by financial technology (fintech) companies – allows consumers to break up purchases into smaller amounts, identical to an installment plan, providing consumers with flexibility to pay desirable amounts for products that may be too expensive to purchase at a single moment while budgeting for other purchases they may depend upon (Wortmann & Lippold, 2023). In fact, recent studies emphasize the large market that has already used BNPL services – over 20% of consumers as of October 2023 (Wang, 2025). Ever since, the payment method has soared in popularity and entices a range of consumers who crave flexible terms that other firms may not offer (Maggio et al., 2022).

Unlike credit cards and other common debt financing methods, BNPL options differ since they typically do not undergo an extensive credit check; rather, they simply request basic personal information and desire a valid bank account or credit card for recurring payments (Pradhan, 2024). As a result, users with minimal or delinquent credit often take advantage of such payment tools, which indirectly deceive consumers due to framing methods employed by fintech companies into purchasing more goods using BNPL, particularly young adults between the ages of 18-24 (Arisandy et al., 2023; Saleh & Terike, 2025). In conjunction, numerous users in the young cohort exhibit insufficient incomes, which – coupled with a high desire for popular

and exclusive products due to impulse – drives irresponsible spending due to flawed perceptions of the debt (Maggio et al., 2022).

Researchers observed such behaviors and contributors – including impulse and minimal initial spend – which drive purchasing when encountered with the option of acquiring goods and/or services, in young adults between 18-25 (Lia & Natswa, 2021; Saleh & Terike, 2025). However, no data on emerging adults has been gathered since this group cannot readily access and utilize BNPL services due to age restrictions among various factors; hence, the lack of data presents a gap that should be analyzed to view of spending patterns in high school students, particularly between the ages of 13-18, in order to predict future financial decisions and intentions once the cohort accesses BNPL services.

Review of Literature

The history of debt financing stretches back thousands of years, though a modern approach of installment credit for materialistic, nonessential goods began in the mid-1800s – ultimately beginning the early variants of BNPL (Akana, 2022). During this time, most forms of credit existed through personal connections within a local community when items, like bicycles and sewing machines, were highly desirable to consumers; at times, credit was secured by putting up collateral to safeguard interests between both parties, often involving a pawnshop or a loan shark (Calder, 2004). As the late-1800s arrived, merchants realized that additional money could be made by offering consumers, specifically those who couldn't afford certain products of high value, installment loans on their goods, uniforming debt financing (Calder, 2004).

During the early-1900s, technological innovation expanded the role of credit tremendously as large companies, including the General Motors Acceptance Corporation, adopted such practices

to a larger segment of middle-income consumers. As the 20th century progressed, the rise of credit cards revolutionized consumer credit by offering flexibility and convenience on purchases, directly influencing consumers to spend even more through monthly payments (Kusmalinda, 2025). By 2000, nearly 70% of households had a general-purpose credit card for financing their purchases and access to credit, largely due to improved telecommunications and computer systems, is higher than before (Calder, 2004).

Today, BNPL services, commonly offered by fintech companies – which employ digital technologies in order to provide financial products and services as an alternative to traditional banking and credit cards – have grown in popularity and sales volume over the past years, supported by the rapid growth between 2019 and 2021 as total loan values grew to \$24.2 billion from \$2 billion (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2022). Major industry leaders of BNPL include Affirm, Afterpay, Klarna, PayPal, Sezzle and Zip, all of whom have capitalized on spending and fees charged to consumers and merchants; in response, numerous traditional banks have introduced different debt financing variants, though an extensive credit history and interest charges are standard, meaning such lenders have more selective measures (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2024; Wortmann & Lippold, 2023).

A major pull factor of BNPL services lies heavily in the minimal initial down payment required to purchase a good or service. Consumers can often select an installment plan, in which they agree to pay a set amount over the course of a few weeks or months – typically breaking a purchase up into four payments over six weeks – often at little or no interest; meanwhile, after the first minimum payment is made, the consumer receives ownership of the goods or services while the lender takes responsibility for collecting payments (Aditya, 2025; Mukhtar et al., 2023). Additionally, since fintech companies aren't considered to be banks, they follow different

regulations and rules, allowing the lenders to extend credit without following extremely strict guidelines, contributing to financial decisions consumers make (Cervellati et al., 2025).

Since most BNPL services operate on the ‘Checkout’ page of e-commerce websites, current consumers feel inclined to take advantage of the installment method to make purchases appear smaller and safer; additionally, many BNPL leaders have begun to offer similar payment methods for in-person transactions as well, instantly approving consumers based on previous purchase behavior (Ashby et al., 2025). For example, users of BNPL can now utilize the service on minor transactions, including grocery shopping and food deliveries, which have been shown to be frequently made by young, financially distressed individuals (Aidala et al., 2024; Kumar et al., 2024). In fact, a study conducted on credit card holders in the United Kingdom revealed that 19.5% of users have charged a BNPL loan to their line of credit, highlighting how consumers attempt to stack their debt to alternative methods in order to take advantage of the low interest rates (Guttman-Kenney et al., 2023). Thus, consumers face a loop of financial burden as they continue to encounter debt from their purchases, often being unable to keep up with their purchases, supplementing future financial repercussions (Consumer Financial Protection Bureau, 2025; Guttman-Kenney et al., 2023).

Certain researchers have observed the various tactics employed by BNPL companies to appeal to potential users. The framing of the desirable features – most notably, zero interest payments – invokes a positive perception about the usage of BNPL in comparison to other payment methods, like a credit card, many of which charge high interest rates (Hayashi & Routh, 2025; Johannesson, 2021; Zaidi, 2021). Although BNPL companies often target young adults through marketing strategies involving website placement, digital advertisements, etc., high school students may be exposed since the cohort often scrolls across social media and initiates

digital purchases; therefore, high school students may also have some degree of susceptibility to such framing or marketing effects of BNPL.

According to a range of studies conducted relating to current perceptions on BNPL and attitudes, specific researchers across developed and emerging markets have gathered various metrics of data – including quantitative purchase transaction data, sales volume, and income. Moreover, qualitative evidence gathered through interviews or short, open-ended surveys helped analyze a consumer's detailed viewpoint and line of reasoning before and after making a purchase with BNPL. Existing research reports consumers face a varying degree of regret after purchasing a product or service since the true cost becomes revealed following installment fulfilment; yet, since BNPL services only require a partial payment to be made initially, the user perceives the cost as quite minimal (Hayashi & Routh, 2025; Qin, 2021). A parallel perception may exist in high school students as well, highlighting potential similarities in attitudes and behavior when purchasing through BNPL services.

Research Gap

As teens enter adulthood, an increase in independence – coupled with purchase behavior – may lead to irresponsible purchases, as demonstrated with individuals between 18-25 today; indeed, as this cohort perceives the debt to be minimal due to framing methods employed by BNPL companies, they may increase the total volume of debt financing used due to poor financial practices (Park, 2025; Qin, 2021). Similarly, it is hypothesized that emerging adults may exhibit an identical perspective regarding debt financing, which, coupled with the lack of financial knowledge and experience, can lead to negative future financial decisions that must be addressed.

Ultimately, this research aims to uncover the gap regarding the influence of BNPL on high school students' perceptions respecting the true cost of a good or service as well as their willingness to use debt financing on various purchases as opposed to paying fully upfront. By doing so, the attitudes of future users of BNPL can be investigated and analyzed to build upon teenage decision making in financial situations and offer additional insight to potential implications as a result of BNPL usage.

Methodology

This study aims to identify a difference, if any, of high school students' perception of affordability and financial risk when using BNPL compared to traditional, upfront payments. In order to address if a difference is observed or not, information regarding purchase decisions would need to be collected through a survey in order to understand the perspectives high school students encounter when facing distinct options for purchasing.

Survey Design

Responses were collected through a simulated, mixed-methods survey design, hosted on Google Forms, primarily attributable to ease of sharing, where respondents were presented a theoretical item for purchase with two different scenarios – a full, upfront payment option and a BNPL payment option. Both payment options involved popular electronic products, featuring Apple AirPods and iPad (or similar equivalent), each hypothetically priced at \$250 (or four payments of \$62.50 for the BNPL option). By doing so, the purchase price point would be reasonably large with affordable installment payments of the same price (Allard et al., 2019). To control for external variables, participants viewed a short description that outlined each hypothetical situation; moreover, participants were assigned a random letter, either A or B, which

corresponded to a particular section that determined the order of the scenarios presented (e.g. Section A presents an upfront scenario as the control segment, followed by a BNPL scenario as the experimental segment).

Participants then indicated their insight on a series of questions (see Figure 1.1) that required a response on a Likert scale between values 1 to 7, designed to measure the affordability and perceived value of both payment methods, one at a time, in order to investigate for any differences, if any, in perceptions (Ashby et al., 2025). By utilizing the Likert scale for such

questions, the strength of student responses could be calculated to determine the extent to which participants would willingly utilize BNPL in addition to other perceived benefits. The means from each question can then be calculated and compared in order to conclude if a difference is exhibited from the various payment

General Information
Name (solely for consent verification purposes)
Age
Gender
Grade Level
Estimated Household Income
Core Sections
Section A or B (this will determine the order the scenarios are presented in)
Likelihood of Purchasing Product in Scenario 1 and 2 (from 1-7)
Affordability of Product in Scenario 1 and 2 (from 1-7)
"Pain" Experienced from Purchasing Product in Scenario 1 and 2 (from 1-7)
Consideration Exhibited Before Purchasing Product in Scenario 1 and 2 (from 1-7)
Potential Financial Risk from Purchasing Product in Scenario 1 and 2 (from 1-7)
Conclusion/Reflection
Noticeable Difference Observed Between Scenario 1 and 2
Previous Awareness of BNPL Prior to Study
Perception of Increased Affordability with BNPL
Future BNPL Usage Consideration (from 1-7) and Explanation
General Questions or Concerns
Any Questions and/or Concerns Regarding the Study.

Figure 1.1 - Questions Presented in Study

methods. In conjunction, paired-sample t-tests were conducted to determine whether a significant difference existed between the options, affirming a true difference is made if $p < .05$. Likewise, Cohen's d effect sizes were calculated using the standard formula in order to specify the magnitude of the difference according to standard benchmarks (0.2 = small, 0.5 = medium, 0.8 = large). Automatic formulas on Google Sheets calculated quantitative statistics, generating figures once formulas and individual data were set.

Participants provided a detailed line of reasoning, a piece of qualitative data, conducive to understand why their perception appears a certain way, supporting individual quantitative responses regarding affordability and likelihood of using the specific payment method – similar to another study, thematically grouping similar attitudes and perspectives regarding high school students' financial literacy (Amiranashvili, 2023). General data collected includes demographic questions, such as age and gender, in order to better comprehend spending differences between groups, if any (e.g. families in a higher income bracket may have distinct spending patterns than families in a lower income bracket). Figure 1.1 highlights the questions asked to the participants as well as the order in which they appeared.

Participants

To measure the extent to which high school students deem BNPL affordable, among other factors, subjects in the study involved students enrolled in a 9th to 12th grade program. For ease of collecting data, participants were solely recruited from Colleyville Heritage High School in Colleyville, Texas, highlighting a limitation to the generalizability of the findings. The total population of students who attend this campus is approximately 1,836. Students who participated identified between the ages of 14 and 18, all of whom were ineligible to use BNPL programs either due to age or insufficient payment method (i.e. no bank account). Participants were recruited through teacher outreach as staff spanning across different courses informed students about the opportunity to participate in the study. To attract potential participants, an incentive was offered, allowing those who completed the survey thoughtfully to enter a raffle in which two winners were selected to earn \$25. Hence, a range of participants completed the study with motivation to thoughtfully respond, which, in effect, increased the total number of responses and eliminated careless submissions.

Before receiving access to the survey, participants completed an informed consent form in addition to obtaining parental consent, in compliance with local campus policies and school district guidelines, since the study involved students. Without the completion of the appropriate consent forms, all students who wished to participate were denied. No details that could compromise the integrity of the study were shared to participants beforehand, though a debrief email informed subjects about the purpose of the study. Participants understood their right to withdraw from the study at any time and revoke their responses if they desired.

Resources Needed

In order to complete the survey, participants utilized their school-issued device to access the Internet, as per school district guidelines. Students who wished to participate were invited to one of many sessions where they completed the survey through a privately communicated URL without a high level of noise or distractions around, preventing inattention and other biases in one's environment. Each participant ensured to commit about 10-15 minutes in order to avoid rushed answers during the survey. Upon submission, responses uploaded onto a Google Sheets file – where information can be reviewed and sorted with advanced settings to visually summarize the data, facilitating result analysis and interpretation.

Risk Assessment and Protection of Privacy

The study involved no risk or discomfort to participants and no controversial topics were presented. Participants understood that the study imposed no risk upon signing up and certain details were explicitly stated on the consent forms. Students were instructed to report any concerns regarding the research, though none were made; additionally, all participants agreed to the terms set and understood their ability to withdraw from the study at any time. These

standards ultimately underlined the importance of ethical standards with proper compliance beyond all local policies and school district guidelines.

In order to verify all consent forms were successfully completed, the names of each participant who completed the forms were collected. Once students responded, their names were automatically cross-referenced with the list of eligible participants and then hidden to remove identifying information. Such measures ensured student privacy and confidentiality in the study while eliminating any researcher bias.

Results and Discussion

A total of 72 student participants completed the survey: half of the participants completed Section A while the other 36 participants completed Section B in order to reduce bias. Participants ranged from ages 14 to 18, with the mean age of participants being 15.94 years. Out of all responses, about 68% were males while the other 32% identified as females. The median grade level for respondents was 10th grade. Additionally, the median estimated household income indicated was between \$100,001 - \$150,000 – which may be attributable to the affluent community surrounding the high school campus. Detailed responses of student demographic data can be found in Figure 2.1.

Participant Demographics	
Age	Quantity
14	6
15	16
16	31
17	14
18	5
Gender	Quantity
Male	49
Female	23
Grade Level	Quantity
9th	12
10th	26
11th	25
12th	9
Estimated Family Income	Quantity
\$0 - \$24k	0
\$24,000 - \$50,000	5
\$50,001 - \$75,000	10
\$75,001 - \$100,000	12
\$100,001 - \$150,000	13
\$150,001 - \$200,000	10
> \$200,000	22

Figure 2.1 - Participant Demographics

Each core section of the survey collected data regarding every student’s perspective on affordability, consideration, and financial risk, among a series of quantitative questions answerable through a numeric value on the Likert scale (1-7). Section A, Part 1 and Section B

Part 2 refer to the upfront option; meanwhile, Section A, Part 2 and Section B, Part 1 refer to the BNPL option. The data tables for the core section quantitative data can be found in Figure 2.2.

In terms of the likelihood of purchasing (higher mean values indicate more likely), student responses in the both upfront options derived a mean of around 4.06 with a standard deviation of approximately 1.73. For both BNPL options, participants expressed a mean likelihood of 4.25 with a standard deviation of approximately 1.81. The paired-samples t-test indicated $p = .53$ and Cohen's d equaled $.07$. The higher mean values for the BNPL sections demonstrate that students may be slightly more likely to purchase something with a payment method that allows them to break down purchases – though the difference is not statistically significant – as supported by the result of the t-test. The effect size is also very small, underlining the minor role of BNPL. The use of electronics in the scenario may have slightly altered participants' likelihood, though not to a great extent.

Next, participants responded to product affordability (higher mean values indicating more affordability) between the hypothetical pricing of either \$250 for the upfront payment or \$62.50 for the BNPL payment option. The mean value of responses derived from both upfront options was nearly 3.82 with a standard deviation of around 1.49. The mean value collected from both BNPL parts was approximately 4.78 with a standard deviation of about 1.54. The paired-samples t-test calculated that $p < .001$ and Cohen's d was approximately $.49$. In other words, participants implied that the BNPL option was more affordable, supported by strong differences in the means. Additionally, the paired-samples t-test revealed that the difference is very significant as students perceived the product to be more affordable at the same price point; furthermore, the effect size yielded a medium result, underlining that the findings may likely affect a moderate to large range of students.

After product affordability, participants were asked to indicate how much it would “hurt” to spend on the products according to price (lower mean values indicate a reduced rate of “hurting” financially). The collected mean value from participants in both upfront payment methods was about 4.4 with a standard deviation of approximately 1.52. The mean value from the scenarios involving BNPL was around 3.76 with a standard deviation of 1.64. The paired-samples t-test calculated that $p < .003$ and Cohen’s d was approximately .37. The fairly lower mean value of the BNPL section reveals that students perceived the installment option to be less harmful and safer. Supported by the statistical tests, the difference between two scenarios is statistically significant with a moderate effect size, underlining that students feel reduced discomfort when breaking down their purchase from a single payment of \$250 to four installments of \$62.50, validating the behavioral economics theory.

The following question asked participants to provide a level of their consideration (higher mean values indicate more consideration) made for each purchase option. In both upfront examples, participants yielded a mean value of around 5.24 with a standard deviation of nearly 1.51. On the other hand, the BNPL option collected a mean value of 5.01 with a standard deviation of about 1.48. The paired-samples t-test calculated p to be approximately .27 while Cohen’s d yielded a value of .13. The lower mean value of the BNPL option underlines that students had slightly less consideration to the item, likely since it appeared to cost less to select participants since \$250 upfront may differ slightly than installments of \$62.50 over time, though the difference was not meaningful; as supported by the statistical tests, the change may be due to chance and the effect size is quite small among those surveyed.

The final question in each core section asked participants to rate the financial risk (higher mean values imply higher financial risk) with each option. In the upfront options, participants

responded with a mean value of around 3.65 alongside a standard deviation of 1.66. In the BNPL portions, participants indicated a mean value of 3.32 with a standard deviation of about 1.55. The paired-samples t-test specified that p was approximately .17 with a Cohen's d value of .16.

Generally, a lower mean was observed in the BNPL scenarios, suggesting that participants' financial risk perception was reduced slightly when breaking up purchases into multiple installments when making a large purchase, though the paired-samples t-test emphasized that the results are not statistically significant. Additionally, the effect size of data was not large enough to create a substantial conclusion regarding the population.

Likelihood of Purchasing			Likelihood of Purchasing			Likelihood of Purchasing			Likelihood of Purchasing		
\bar{x}	Section A, Part 1 (Upfront Option)		\bar{x}	Section A, Part 2 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 1 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 2 (Upfront Option)	
4.22	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.08	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.42	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.89	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses
More Likely →	1	3	More Likely →	1	5	More Likely →	1	2	More Likely →	1	2
	2	3		2	2		2	4		2	7
	3	6		3	6		3	6		3	5
	4	9		4	6		4	6		4	11
	5	6		5	10		5	7		5	5
	6	4		6	3		6	5		5	2
	7	5		7	4		7	6		6	7
Product Affordability			Product Affordability			Product Affordability			Product Affordability		
\bar{x}	Section A, Part 1 (Upfront Option)		\bar{x}	Section A, Part 2 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 1 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 2 (Upfront Option)	
3.72	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.58	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.97	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.92	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses
More Affordable →	1	1	More Affordable →	1	1	More Affordable →	1	1	More Affordable →	1	2
	2	6		2	3		2	1		2	6
	3	8		3	4		3	4		3	7
	4	11		4	9		4	6		4	9
	5	8		5	8		5	11		5	6
	6	1		6	7		8	6		6	2
	7	1		7	4		7	7		7	4
"Hurts" to Spend			"Hurts" to Spend			"Hurts" to Spend			"Hurts" to Spend		
\bar{x}	Section A, Part 1 (Upfront Option)		\bar{x}	Section A, Part 2 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 1 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 2 (Upfront Option)	
3.92	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.53	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.00	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.89	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses
"Hurts" More →	1	1	"Hurts" More →	1	4	"Hurts" More →	1	1	"Hurts" More →	1	1
	2	9		2	7		2	7		2	1
	3	4		3	7		3	4		3	3
	4	7		4	10		4	12		4	5
	5	8		5	2		5	7		5	15
	6	7		6	4		6	1		6	8
	7	0		7	2		7	4		7	3
Consideration Made			Consideration Made			Consideration Made			Consideration Made		
\bar{x}	Section A, Part 1 (Upfront Option)		\bar{x}	Section A, Part 2 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 1 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 2 (Upfront Option)	
4.97	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	4.75	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	5.28	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	5.50	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses
More Consideration →	1	1	More Consideration →	1	0	More Consideration →	1	1	More Consideration →	1	1
	2	3		2	5		2	0		2	0
	3	1		3	2		3	1		3	3
	4	7		4	8		4	8		4	3
	5	10		5	7		5	10		5	5
	6	7		6	10		6	8		6	17
	7	7		7	4		7	8		7	7
Financial Risk			Financial Risk			Financial Risk			Financial Risk		
\bar{x}	Section A, Part 1 (Upfront Option)		\bar{x}	Section A, Part 2 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 1 (BNPL Option)		\bar{x}	Section B, Part 2 (Upfront Option)	
3.47	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.19	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.44	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses	3.83	Likert Scale Value	Student Responses
More Risky →	1	4	More Risky →	1	4	More Risky →	1	3	More Risky →	1	4
	2	7		2	10		2	6		2	3
	3	9		3	7		3	15		3	9
	4	7		4	8		4	3		4	6
	5	4		5	5		5	5		5	10
	6	3		6	1		6	1		6	1
	7	2		7	1		7	3		7	3

Figure 2.2 - Core Section Question Breakdown

Following the core sections, participants proceeded to the conclusion and reflection portion of the study, in which they responded regarding their attitude towards BNPL and potential future usage. Participants pointed out their likelihood of utilizing BNPL (higher mean values indicate more likely) in the future was 3.89 based on the Likert scale.

Additionally, students answered if BNPL makes purchases appear more affordable, regardless of their likelihood of utilizing the payment type. Out of all 72 participants, 55 students (76.4%) reported that BNPL does make purchases seem more affordable while the remaining 17 participants (23.6%) mentioned otherwise. A qualitative question was asked to capture each participant's reasoning for why BNPL may seem like a more affordable option. Each line of reasoning could be categorized into one of six general reasons, found in Figure 2.3. Of those that noted BNPL does appear to be a more affordable option, 33 respondents primarily noted the smaller increments associated with the payment method that made the purchase feel more affordable. Meanwhile, 13 and 9 participants, respectively, indicated that the longer time period

General Attitude About BNPL Affordability		
Option	Quantity	%
Smaller Increments	33	46%
Longer Time Period	13	18%
Low Down Payment	9	13%
Lack of Financial Resources	5	7%
Full Payment Made Regardless	9	13%
Risk of Overpayment	3	4%

Figure 2.3 - Participant BNPL Attitudes

and the low down payment was the primary reason for

BNPL affordability. Out of those who expressed that

BNPL does not make payments more affordable, 5

participants noted that their personal lack of financial

resources at the time of purchase would deter them from

purchasing. On the other hand, 9 participants argued that the purchase price would be the same

regardless of payment method while 3 participants noted the risk of overpayment in the case of

late payments. Indeed, although some students pinpointed flaws with BNPL, most actually

preferred it due to financial flexibility – a similar pull factor found among current users of

BNPL. However, this perspective may hinder the plurality of students from understanding the full payment terms as they perceive the total amount to be meager.

Using estimated household income range information collected from participants, data was compared between the amount of potential disposable income and attitudes regarding BNPL For

BNPL Affordability Categorized by Income Range					
Estimated Income Range	Total	BNPL More Affordable?		Attitudes about BNPL	Responses
\$24,000 - \$50,000	5	Yes	4	Smaller Increments	2
				Longer Time Period	2
		No	1	Lack of Financial Resources	1
\$50,001 - \$75,000	10	Yes	9	Smaller Increments	5
				Longer Time Period	4
		No	1	Full Payment Made Regardless	1
\$75,001 - \$100,000	12	Yes	10	Smaller Increments	8
				Longer Time Period	1
				Low Down Payment	1
		No	2	Lack of Financial Resources	1
				Full Payment Made Regardless	1
\$100,001 - \$150,000	13	Yes	9	Smaller Increments	4
				Longer Time Period	3
				Low Down Payment	2
		No	4	Full Payment Made Regardless	3
				Risk of Overpayment	1
\$150,001 - \$200,000	10	Yes	6	Smaller Increments	4
				Longer Time Period	1
				Low Down Payment	1
		No	4	Lack of Financial Resources	2
				Full Payment Made Regardless	1
> \$200,000	22	Yes	17	Smaller Increments	10
				Longer Time Period	2
				Low Down Payment	5
		No	5	Lack of Financial Resources	1
				Full Payment Made Regardless	3
				Risk of Overpayment	1

Figure 2.4 - Affordability Perspectives Categorized by Income Range

participants with an estimated household income of \$24,000 - \$50,000, 4 out of 5 respondents pointed out that BNPL was more affordable, mainly attributable to tiny increments and an extended time period to finance purchases. For students with an estimated household income of \$50,001 - \$75,000, 9 out of the 10 respondents mentioned that the smaller increments and longer time period to finance

purchases made BNPL appear more affordable. Out of all the respondents with an estimated household income of \$75,001 - \$100,000, 10 out of 12 of the participants indicated BNPL felt more economical, primarily due to the division of payments into manageable increments.

Students with an estimated household income of \$100,001 - \$150,000 indicated that 9 out of the 13 respondents felt BNPL felt more affordable, though the proportion was slightly decreased

than students with lower household incomes. Furthermore, students who reported an estimated household income of \$150,001 - \$200,000 noted that 6 out of 10 respondents felt BNPL was more affordable. Similarly, 17 out of 22 participants who identified their estimated household income to be over \$200,000 reported that BNPL was an economical option. As the proportion of students who felt BNPL was more affordable typically decreased while household income increased, a slight, negative correlation is observed between the two variables. Across these groups, a major factor that deterred participants from BNPL was the similar purchase price, regardless of payment method, as expressed by 7 out of 13 respondents. Figure 2.4 outlines the responses and perceptions of respondents categorized by income ranges. Overall, the trend suggests that as income increases, students are generally less likely to finance purchases. This can be supported by the characteristics of existing BNPL users – though an increasing number of those in higher income brackets have shifted to adopt the debt financing method.

Prior to the study's completion, students revealed whether they had encountered BNPL previously in order to determine an approximate percentage of students who may have been exposed to the payment method. Responses collected from the students highlight that 35 out of 72 (48.6%) of the respondents have heard of BNPL while the other 37 (51.4%) have not, as illustrated by Figure 2.5. Although the majority of students have not yet encountered BNPL or understood the various terms involved with the payment method prior to the study, the majority of respondents are still likely to trust it and perceive BNPL as more affordable than upfront payments after learning about the installment options. This striking data contributes to the impulsive behavior commonly associated with

Heard of BNPL?	
Option	Student Quantity
Yes	35
No	37

Figure 2.5 - Student's Exposure to BNPL

young adults, demonstrating how this cohort may generate financial decisions solely based on perception without considering personal financial stability.

Implications

The findings of the study suggest that high school students are likely to exhibit similar perspectives to common users of BNPL in terms of product affordability and discomfort when purchasing, – directly following key concepts of the behavioral economics theory. To prevent these young adults from collapsing into high amounts of debt and experiencing regret post-purchase – as do many users of BNPL – high school students should be knowledgeable about such payment options, alongside the importance of saving and credit. Teaching students, especially those from less affluent backgrounds, about financial literacy encourages students to make informed decisions when producing financial decisions in real world situations before they become 18 years old. Such education can be completed through courses within the foundational curriculum in schools or external programs designed for the cohort to brace themselves financially. Additionally, high school students should grasp the effects of framing methods employed by fintech companies to interpret affordability as unchanged. Furthermore, banks and fintech companies should consider arranging stricter guidelines with higher transparency, similar to credit card issuers who follow rigid guidelines, before entering into BNPL agreements to ensure consumers fully understand fees or consequences that may be added on with such installment plans. By doing so, borrowers acknowledge their purchases with an open understanding, reducing the effects of post-purchase regret while limiting impulsive actions.

Limitations

The study involved some limitations that impact the generalizability of the results, primarily noting the relatively small size of the sample since the population involved high school students

through the use of convenience sampling to acquire participants, limiting the range of participants to a single high school. With extended capabilities across various schools in conjunction with a lengthy time frame, students from across the nation could be recruited to derive more reliable results. In order to make more precise conclusions between distinct income ranges, recruiting additional students with diverse household income ranges would help account for differences between the group demographics that may impact collective usage of BNPL. Since a small sample size was collected in a relatively affluent population for this study, results may be skewed and could affect the validity of the results; hence, it is suggested that a greater sample size with even groups is conducted in order to generate more effective statistics. Additionally, the implementation of a hypothetical scenario may appear different than actual situations in which students would purchase something of monetary value; as a result, differences in perspectives, including affordability and risk, may be observed if real purchases were made, though this age group is unable to utilize actual BNPL installment plans due to age or financial factors. By pushing students to lose something of value – potentially through a fake money system – more realistic outcomes could be observed.

Recommendations

Future researchers may consider the effects of BNPL on high school students across a larger scope, typically across the country, in order to account for regional differences and obtain data within various demographics. Through this, conclusions can be drawn that are more applicable to the entire population of high school students, which may help determine collective financial literacy and potentially contribute to the implementation of curriculum crafted to prepare students as they approach adulthood. If students are in a financial literacy course, or its equivalent, a similar study could be conducted both before and after the school year in order to

determine if perspectives modify, which may provide insight regarding its effectiveness as a solution. Additionally, longitudinal studies may serve as a useful method of measuring student perceptions as shifts can occur once students become more mature and financially conscious. This way, researchers can continue to view potential changes over a period of time that may highlight the role of repeated exposure, among other factors students remain prone to.

Conclusion

As high school students approach adulthood and may rely on forms of credit to help assist in purchasing products and services, BNPL presents itself as a desirable method of debt financing in order to reduce financial burden, supported by its use from consumers worldwide. In order to determine if high school students' exposure to such systems plays a significant role in perceived affordability and financial risk, among some variables, participants conducted two similar hypothetical purchases – one using BNPL and the other using upfront payment at the same total price point. Results conclude that the perception of affordability significantly increased under the BNPL section since students could break down the purchase into smaller installments. Additionally, the pain of paying the total cost was reduced since the longer period of time provided flexibility to students. However, purchase consideration and risk perception did not significantly change between the two scenarios, underlining key points for future researchers to study and clarify. Hence, BNPL altered student perceptions when purchasing products and motivated students to rely on the debt financing method – notably with minimal prior information regarding it – emphasizing the sensitive nature of adolescents when framing effects are employed. Future studies should look to expand the sample of students and collect

sophisticated data over a period of time in order to fully address variables tested in the study as BNPL continues to grow as a payment option across the world, shaping financial cognition.

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